

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Trivalent Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium, Neodymium and Samarium Complexes with 2-(*p*-sulphophenylazo) 1, 8-Dihydroxy naphthalene 3, 6-Disulphonic Acid (Trisodium salt) [SPADNS]

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The stepwise proton-ligand stability constants of SPADNS and its metal complexes with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous solution. Stability constants of these complexes were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti at 20° and 40° at an ionic strength of 0.1M (NaClO₄). The trend in the stability constant values of these metal chelates has been found to be

The values of overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying complex formation have also been calculated.

A survey of the literature revealed that some studies¹⁻⁵ have been made spectrophotometrically on the complexation reactions of SPADNS with different metal ions, however, no attempt appears to have been made to evaluate the stability constant and thermodynamic parameters of Lanthanide complexes with SPADNS pH-metrically. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make the study of Lanthanides-SPADNS system potentiometrically.

Experimental

The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of metal oxides (BDH, AnalaR Grade) La₂O₃, Pr₂O₃, Nd₂O₃, Sm₂O₃ and nitrates such as Ce(NO₃)₃ in minimum quantities of perchloric acid. The excess of acid was removed by evaporating the solution four to five times with double distilled water. These solutions were standardized by oxalate method⁶. The stock solutions of SPADNS (Fluka), sodium perchlorate (Riedel), perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide were prepared in the usual manner.

pH measurements were carried out with extended scale Phillips pH-meter model PR 9405 M with glass and calomel electrodes. pH-meter was calibrated using Cambridge buffer tablets of pH 4 and 7. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen in a specially designed double-walled beaker of capacity about 250 ml made of Pyrex glass using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique^{7,8} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁹.

Three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows :

A : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid, B : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand and C : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion solution such that the concentration of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. The ratio of the metal and ligand was always 1 : 6. An appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate (2.0M) was added to maintain 0.1M ionic strength. The mixtures A, B and C were individually titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.4M).

Results and Discussion

In order to calculate the stability constants of the metal complexes, it is necessary to calculate the proton-ligand stability constants. To calculate the formation constant of the proton-ligand system, the value of $\bar{n}A$ at different pH values were calculated using the acid, ligand titration curves (solutions A and B) using Irving and Rossotti method⁹.

A proton-ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting the values of $\bar{n}A$ against pH values. The proton-ligand stability constants were obtained using the various computational techniques which are given below in Table 1.

The degree of formation of the complex (\bar{n}) and the negative logarithm of the free ligand concentration (pL) at a particular pH value were calculated with the help of ligand and metal titration curves (solution B & C) using Irving and Rossotti method⁹.

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TABLE-1. PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SPADNS
0.1M (NaClO₄)

Method employed	TEMPERATURE					
	20°			40°		
	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log β ^H	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log β ^H
1. Interpolation of half \bar{n} values ^{7,8}	10.35	9.15	19.50	9.65	8.65	18.30
2. Correction term method ¹⁰	10.27	9.15	19.42	9.57	8.71	18.28
3. Least square treatment						
(a) Method of simultaneous equation ¹⁰	10.2	9.23	19.43	9.52	8.84	18.36
(b) Curve fitting method ¹¹	10.28	9.07	19.35	9.67	8.60	18.28
Mean value	10.27	9.15	19.42	9.60	8.70	18.3

TABLE-2. METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES (log K₁) AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Metal ion	Method employed	log K ₁		ΔH°(K.cal.mol ⁻¹)	ΔS°(cal.mol ⁻¹ ° ⁻¹)
		20°	40°		
La ³⁺	A	6.95	6.70	-4.58	13.9
	B	6.95	6.77		
	C	6.95	6.70		
	Mean value	6.95	6.72		
Ce ³⁺	A	7.20	6.95	-6.86	7.6
	B	7.38	6.98		
	C	7.20	7.20		
	Mean value	7.26	7.04		
Pr ³⁺	A	7.70	7.40	-8.67	3.46
	B	7.81	7.34		
	C	7.80	7.50		
	Mean value	7.77	7.41		
Nd ³⁺	A	8.00	7.65	-9.84	0.89
	B	8.18	7.67		
	C	8.20	7.65		
	Mean value	8.13	7.66		
Sm ³⁺	A	8.60	8.25	-5.72	16.88
	B	8.55	8.30		
	C	8.60	8.30		
	Mean value	8.57	8.28		

Method A : refers to interpolation at half \bar{n} values ;
B : refers to least square treatment (curve fitting) ;
C : refers to pointwise calculation method.

A metal-ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting the values of \bar{n} against pL values. The value of \bar{n} does not exceed 1 in all the cases, indicating thereby the formation of only 1 : 1 complex. The values of log K₁ were determined by various computational techniques which are given in Table 2. The value of log K₁ was also obtained by the pointwise calculation method using the following equation :

$$\log K_1 = pL - \log(1 - \bar{n})/\bar{n}$$

The values of overall changes in free energy ($\Delta^\circ G$) enthalpy ($\Delta^\circ H$) and entropy ($\Delta^\circ S$) accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined applying the standard equations given below¹² :

$$\Delta^\circ G = -RT \ln \beta$$

The value of $\Delta^\circ H$ was determined by temperature coefficient method as well as from the isobar equation

$$\frac{d \ln \beta}{dT} = \frac{\Delta^\circ H}{RT^2}$$

Assuming $\Delta^\circ H$ to be constant over a narrow range of temperature, this can be written as

$$\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta^\circ H}{4.576}$$

The value of $\Delta^\circ S$ was calculated from the relation

$$\Delta^\circ S = \frac{\Delta^\circ H - \Delta^\circ G}{T}$$

The values of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2. The values of protonation constants given in Table 1 show a decreasing tendency with increase in temperature. In all the systems the values of log K₁ at 20° are greater than those at 40° indicating that the low temperature is favourable for

the complex formation. The trend in overall stability of these complexes is $\text{Sm}^{+3} > \text{Nd}^{+3} > \text{Pr}^{+3} > \text{Ce}^{+3} > \text{La}^{+3}$ at 20° and 40°. This is in accordance with the general rule that the stability of Lanthanide complexes increases with the decrease in ionic radii of Lanthanides.

The formation of Lanthanides-SPADNS complexes is spontaneous process which is evident from the more negative values of ΔG° with increase in temperature. The negative values of ΔH° ensures that the reaction is exothermic. The values of ΔS° are positive in all the cases indicating that entropy is favourable for the complex formation.

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